

How did the pandemic crisis affect the financial, economic, and social performance of social enterprises? Insights from Italian social cooperatives

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Introduction

The Covid-19 crisis affected the world's economic and social system in many ways. Social Enterprises (SEs) play a necessary role in delivering social value during such crises (Bacq and Lumpkin, 2020; Sarma et al., 2022; Weaver, 2020). However, there is still a lack of empirical evidence that analyzes the impact of the pandemic on the performance of SEs and how that performance differs from "non-social" companies.

This study compares two types of organizations in the Italian context: social cooperatives (SCs) and private limited companies (PLCs). We use ratio analysis in a three-dimensional perspective: economic, financial, and social, where the latter concerns the ability to create and distribute value-added to stakeholders (Riahi-Belkaoui, 1996; Landis et al., 2014).

Methods

We carry out a comparative analysis using the same financial, economic and social performance ratios.

Data are extracted from the AIDA database on the entire population of Italian SCs and PLCs with between 5 and 250 employees.

The analysis is limited to the sectors of economic activity in which the SCs mainly operate (Poledrini and Tortia, 2020): ATECO 87 (residential social assistance services) and 88 (non-residential social assistance).

We use a short panel of years from 2018 to 2021 to capture pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic conditions.

Though the descriptive results are very informative, we also conducted more rigorous testing: two-sided t-tests of means between the two corporate forms and OLS regression with each of the nine ratios as the dependent variable.

Results

Based on the results of the comparative analysis on the SCs and PLCs data, an approach also focused on the social dimension can be considered correct.

Value added created and the return rate of total assets in terms of value added show a clear superiority in the social dimension of the SC model.

Data relating to the year 2020 show a higher level of resilience in SCs compared with PLCs and the results of the different ratios in 2021 demonstrate a more effective and stronger response of SCs in terms of recovery with respect to the PLCs benchmark.

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